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Report on soil fauna

D3

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WP3 - Soil macro- meso- and microfauna functional diversity

CSIC-INIA, CSIC-EBD

Task 3.1. Soil microfauna functional diversity - CSIC-INIA, CSIC-EBD

Nematodes were extracted from by Baermann funnels (Barker, 1985) from soil samples collected in 8 core sites. Once extracted, all nematodes in each sample were counted under a binocular and 100 individuals were classified into functional groups. All nematode abundances were expressed as no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil. To check for differences in nematode functional group composition across CS, linear models were used, while linear mixed models were used to assess the effects of treatments on nematode numbers with CS and block and random factors. All analyses were run on the R software (R core team, 2022).

Nematodes were classified into six functional groups (Yeates, 1993; Ferris et al., 2001):

- **Opportunistic bacterivores:** Bacterial-feeding nematodes that respond rapidly to increases in bacterial biomass. When the soil is fertilized or amended with organic products, bacterial biomass rapidly increases, and such increase is followed by a rapid enhancement of opportunistic bacterivore populations
- **Generalist bacterivores:** Bacterial-feeding nematodes that do not respond so fast to enrichment, with more stable populations and extremely resistant to environmental perturbation.
- **Fungal feeding nematodes:** Nematodes that feed on soil fungi by piercing fungal hyphas with a stylet.
- **Root associates:** plant-feeding nematodes that feed on root hair, with a limited damage potential to plant health.
- **Plant-parasitic nematodes:** Endo- and ecto-parasites that feed on plant root with medium to high damage potential to plant health.

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- Omnivores: nematodes able to feed in plants and other soil animals by piercing the food source with a stylet.
- Predators: nematodes that feed on other soil animals (including other nematodes) either by piercing with a stylet or by ingesting them.

Total nematode abundances ranged between 331.1 and 6311.8 nematodes /100 g of dry soil. Mean nematode abundances per core site ranged between 885.1 (CS1, Italy) to 3186.2 (CS3, France) (Fig.1) and an absolute mean of 1751.3 nematodes per 100g dry soil. Nematode numbers significantly varied across CS ($F=5.68$, $p<0.05$).

Fig. 1. Total no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil (tot) at different CS1 (CREA, Italy), CS2 (INRAE, France), CS3 (INRAE, France), CS4 (Aarhus Univ., Denmark), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, The Netherlands), CS7 (LAMMC, Lithuania), and CS9 (CRAW, Belgium).

Total no. of nematodes also varied across treatments. Nematode abundances at T1 (*first agroecological practice*) was significantly lower ($t= -2.21$, $p< 0.05$) than T3 (*conventional practice*) (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2. Total no. of nematodes /100 g of dry soil (tot) at agroecological practices (T1, T2) compared to a standard control (T3).

A constrained redundancy analysis was used to test whether functional group community composition varied across CS and treatments. The resulting ordination (Fig. 3) was significant ($F=7.45$, $p<0.05$), with CS presenting a stronger influence on the ordination ($F=9.02$, $p>0.05$) than treatments ($F=1.93$, $p=0.07$).

Fig. 3. Constrained RDA ordination showing the influence of CS and treatments on nematode community functional composition. Ba = bacterivores, Fu = fungivores, Pp = plant-parasites, Root = Root-associates, Om = Omnivores, P = predators, Ben_pest = ratio beneficial to pest nematodes. Rel = relative abundances.

The effect of treatments on the absolute and relative abundances of nematode functional groups and on the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes was assessed in the whole data set with linear mixed models with CS and block as random factors. Only 3 variables responded to the agroecological treatments (Fig. 4). The relative abundance of root associates was significantly ($t=-2.26$, $p>0.05$) higher in T2 (14.5%) compared to T3 (9.7%), probably responding to increased plant and root biomass in such treatment. The total abundance of omnivores was significantly higher in T1 (4.6%, $t=2.75$, $p>0.05$) than in T3 (2.8%), while the abundance in T2 (3.4%) was marginally

significant ($t=1.94$, $p=0.05$). Finally, the ratio beneficial to herbivore nematodes was significantly ($t=-2.26$, $p<0.05$) lower (6.8) in T2 than in T3 (7.11).

Fig. 4. Relative abundance of root associates, absolute abundances of omnivores, and ratio beneficial to herbivore nematodes in the agroecological treatments across all CS. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

The relatively low response of nematode communities at the large scale level, probably due to the experimental design heterogeneity, requires of the analyses of each case study separately. At CS2 (INRAE) no differences were detected among soil management practices.

CS1 (CREA)

At the CREA experiment, only the relative abundance of plant-parasites responded to treatments, showing a significant ($F= 4.56$, $p<0.05$) increase in T2, the treatment with mixed cover crops in between-tree alleys (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Relative abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes (Pp_rel) at different agroecological management practices.

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CS3 (INRAE)

The experiment at CS2 (INRAE) only compared two agroforestry systems: a system with a crop rotation in the tree alleys with tillage (T3) and a system with no tillage and perennial grass in the alleys. Nematodes greatly responded to such practices, showing a significantly lower no. of total nematodes ($F= 24.42$, $p<0.05$), total and relative abundances of opportunistic bacterivores ($F= 170.8$ and $F= 13.35$, $p<0.05$), total fungivores abundances ($F= 12.65$, $p>0.05$), higher relative and absolute abundances of omnivores ($F = 11.53$ and $F= 2498$, $p<0.05$), and a marginally significantly higher relative abundances of root-associates ($F= 5.19$, $p=0.09$) and lower ratio beneficial to pest nematodes ($F= 4.71$, $p=0.09$) in the agroecological treatment compared to the control. Some of these differences are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Relative abundances nematode functional groups at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS4 (AU)

The experiment at Aarhus University compares a monoculture (*Lolium perenne*) crop with two diversified systems with 2 and 6 plant spp. The relative abundance of opportunistic nematodes ($F = 5.38$, $p < 0.05$) and of omnivore nematodes ($F = 4.24$, $p < 0.05$) significantly increased in T1 compared to T3 (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Relative abundances of opportunistic bacterivores nematodes and omnivores at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS5 (INIA-CSIC)

The CS5 (INIA-CSIC) compares different tillage and crop rotation combinations. The control (T3) consist of wheat monoculture with minimum tillage, T1 consists of wheat monoculture with no-tillage and T2 is a crop rotation and no-tillage system. The comparison among treatments showed significantly lower nematode numbers ($F = 4.31$, $p < 0.05$), and abundances of bacterivores ($F = 4.56$, $p < 0.05$) and fungivores ($F = 4.16$, $p < 0.05$), in T1 and T2 compared to the control, while the absolute ($F = 9.85$, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 8) and relative ($F = 4.89$, $p < 0.05$) abundances of omnivores were significantly higher.

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Fig. 8. Absolute abundances of total nematodes and bacterivores, fungivores, and omnivore nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS6 (WUR)

The experiment at WUR compares 2 cover crop systems with 2 (T1) and 3 (T2) plant species with a fallow control (T3). In such systems, only the relative abundance of fungivores responded to management, showing significantly ($F = 5.01$, $p < 0.05$) higher values in the agroecological treatments (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Relative abundances of fungivores nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS7 (LAMMC)

The management practices tested at LAMMC only showed significant effects on a single nematode group. The experiment compares a conventional tillage system (T3) with no tillage (T1) and no-tillage plus cover crops (T2) systems. Only the absolute abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes ($F = p < 0.05$) was significantly higher in T2 than in the control (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Absolute abundances of plant-parasitic nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

CS9 (CRAW)

The experiment at CRAW compares 3 rotation systems with different residue management. In the control (T3) crop residues are exported, while in T1 farmyard manure is used as organic amendment and in T2 residues remain in the field and cover crops are sowed. Only the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes responded significantly, with lower values at the agroecological treatment (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Ratio beneficial to pest nematodes at different agroecological management practices. See Fig. 3 for functional group abbreviations.

Conclusions

Considering all the obtained results, it results evident that the T2 treatment (the management practices with a higher agroecological component) exerted a stronger effect on the nematode community than T1 (Table 1). In general, both treatments *decrease* the absolute abundances of bacterivores and fungivores, leading to a decrease in the total number of nematodes in the community. In five of the CS experiments, the tested agroecological treatments included the reduction in the tillage intensity. In previous studies (refs), the reduction of tillage implies a significant reduction of the amount of organic matter incorporated into the soil after the crop cycle ends. Such reduction of organic inputs might decrease available resources for soil microbes and consequently a reduction in the total abundances of bacterivore and fungivore nematodes. Oppositely, the absolute abundances of omnivore nematodes, more sensitive to physical perturbation than bacterivores and omnivores (ref)

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increased in T1 and T2. In T2, an increase of the total number of plant-parasitic nematodes was also detected, probably due to an increase in plant root biomass associated to such systems.

Table 1. Significant effects detected in the CS experiments. Each effect is a significant change detected in T1 or T2 compared to T3 at a given CS.

T1		T2	
Increase	Decrease	Increase	Decrease
<i>Om_tot</i>	tot	<i>Om_tot</i>	<i>Ba_tot</i>
<i>Om_rel</i>	<i>Ba_tot</i>	<i>Om_tot</i>	<i>Ba_tot</i>
<i>Fu_rel</i>	<i>Ben_pest</i>	<i>Pp_tot</i>	<i>Ba1_tot</i>
<i>Ba1_rel</i>	<i>Fu_tot</i>	<i>Root_rel</i>	<i>Ben_pest</i>
		<i>Fu_rel</i>	<i>Ben_pest</i>
		<i>Pp_rel</i>	<i>Fu_tot</i>
			<i>Fu_tot</i>
			tot
			tot

The percentage contribution of nematode trophic groups also changed in agroecological systems. An increase in the contribution of omnivores, root-associates, and plant-parasitic nematodes were also detected, probably due to a reduction in soil perturbation and the already mentioned increased resources available for herbivores. In general, the size of the whole nematode community decreased, so, in spite of the reduction in bacterivore and fungivore absolute numbers, the % contribution of such nematodes to the community occasionally increased. In both systems, the change in nematode community structure resulted in a reduction of the ratio beneficial to pest nematodes.

Task 3.2. Soil mesofauna functional diversity - CSIC-EEZA, CSIC-INIA

Samples have been extracted by Berlese funnels and all animals preserved in alcohol. All individuals are being counted and separated into main mesofaunal groups: mites (Acari), springtails (Collembola), symphylans (Symphyla), proturans (Protura) diplurans (Diplura), pauropods (Pauropoda) Thysanoptera, and encytraeids (Enchytraeidae).

Task 3.3. Soil macrofauna functional diversity - CSIC-EBD, CSIC-IPE

Earthworms have been collected in CS1 (Italy), CS6 (The Netherlands), CS7 (Lithuania), and CS9 (Belgium). CS5 (Spain) was sampled but no earthworms were found, and another sampling will occur during winter. Individuals are being identified.

Soil macroarthropods were sampled with pitfall traps in cereal crops at four core-sites: CS3 (Mauguio-INRAE, France), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, Netherlands), and CS9 (CRA-W, Belgium). Traps (2.5 cm ø, 5 cm deep, with a mixture of 70 % ethanol and 30 % monoethylene glycol) were active during four days in spring and all the caught arthropods were preserved in alcohol. All ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) were counted and identified. Using the data of the presence and abundance of the different ant species from the pitfall traps, a matrix of species abundance was constructed for the 48 different plots sampled in this study (12 plots/site x 4 sites). For each plot we used the total abundance for each species (the sum of five pitfalls). Other ecological indexes calculated were: species richness (S, number of ant species), Shannon's diversity index (H) and Pielou's evenness index (J) (details of calculations in Cerdá et al. 2012). All analyses were run on the R software (R core team, 2022).

Ant **species richness** at the study plots ranged between 11 species (CS5, Spain) and only one species (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean (\pm SD) of 3.1 ± 2.5 species per plot. Ant richness significantly varied across core sites (GLM, $\text{Chi}^2=366.52$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences, the highest richness value being that of CS5 (Spain), followed by CS3 (France) and then the very low values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 12A)

Total **ant abundance** at the study plots ranged between 327 and 0 worker / 5 pitfall traps. Mean ant abundance per plot at the core sites ranged between 3.25 (CS9, Belgium) to 156.6 workers (CS3, France) (Fig.12B) and an absolute mean (\pm SD) of 92.6 ± 95.1 workers per plot. Ant numbers significantly varied across core sites (GLM, $\text{Chi}^2=78.87$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis

showed significant differences, the highest mean abundance values being those of CS5 (Spain) and CS3 (France) (between which there are no significant differences), followed by CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (Fig. 12B).

Mean **ant diversity** (measured with the Shannon-Weaver index) at the study plots ranged between 1.570 (CS5, Spain) and 0.00 (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean diversity (\pm SD) per plot of 0.643 ± 0.616 . Ant diversity significantly varied across core

sites ($\text{Chi}^2=562.41$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences, the highest diversity value being that of CS5 (Spain), followed by CS3 (France) and then the very low values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 12C).

Mean **ant evenness** (measured with the Pielou index) at the study plots ranged between 0.774 (CS5, Spain) and 0.00 (CS9, Belgium), and an absolute mean evenness ($\pm\text{SD}$) per plot of 0.414 ± 0.377 . Ant evenness significantly varied across core sites ($\text{Chi}^2=446.73$, $p<0.0001$), and contrast analysis showed significant differences between two groups of core sites: the higher evenness values being those of CS5 (Spain) and CS3 (France) and the lower values at CS6 (Netherlands) and CS9 (Belgium) (between which there are no significant differences) (Fig. 12D).

The Shannon diversity index takes into account both the number of species (richness) and their relative abundance. The Pielou evenness index ranges from 1 – when all species are equally abundant, to 0 – when all individuals in the sample belong to the same species. From our results, it is evident that there are two sites with a high ant abundance, species richness and diversity: CS5 and CS3; and the other two northernmost sites (CS9 and CS6) have much less abundance, richness and diversity of ants. Concerning the evenness of ant assemblages, in the southern core sites evenness have higher values (higher than 0.7), which means that the species present have a fairly homogeneous distribution (similar relative abundances), while in the northern core sites evenness values are very low, in CS9 (Belgium), because there is only one ant species (*Lasius niger*), and in CS6 (Netherlands) there are two ant species (*Lasius niger* and *Myrmica specioides*), but *L. niger* is much more abundant.

These differences between core sites could also be related to the local faunas (Table 2). Local ant faunas of the countries of the core sites follow a latitudinal gradient, with higher species richness in the southernmost sites (Spain and France, with 296 and 181 ant species, respectively) and lower richness in the northernmost sites (Belgium and Netherlands, with 97 and 78 ant species, respectively).

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Table 2 – Comparison between the total ant species richness in the different countries and the local ant richness at the study core sites

Country	Number of ant species ¹	N of ant species at CS ²	Total abundance at CS ³	Local precipitation (mean total values at each CS)
Spain (CS5)	296	11	1852	389 mm/year
France (CS3)	181	7	1879	740 mm/year
Belgium (CS9)	97	1	39	730 mm/year
Netherlands (CS6)	78	2	674	895 mm/year

¹ Source: https://www.antwiki.org/wiki/Diversity_by_Country (Access 15 August 2024)

² Total number of ant species in the 12 plots at each core site.

³ Sum of worker abundance in the 60 pitfall traps / core site.

Total species richness, ant abundance, ant diversity and ant evenness did not vary across **treatments**. Mean values of all analysed ant ecological indices did not show statistically significant differences between T1 (*first agroecological practice*), T2 (*second agroecological practice*) and T3 (*conventional practice*) (GLM, see details in Figure 13).

Fig. 13. Mean values (\pm SD) of different ant ecological indices in the different treatments: two agroecological practices (T1, T2) and conventional practice as standard control (T3) A. Total no. of ants (abundance). B. Ant species richness. C. Shannon diversity index. D. Pielou evenness index.

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According with their main food items (Arnan et al. 2015), the ant species were classified into three functional (trophic) groups:

- Seed-eaters. Granivorous ants. The most important component of the diet are seeds. As they are seed predators, these ants can have a negative effect on plant populations.
- Insect-eaters. Scavenger ants. Mainly collect arthropod corpses. Scavenging has a positive ecosystem effect through nutrient redistribution
- Liquid food eaters. Sources of liquid food are Homoptera honeydew (aphid-tending ants) or nectar of flowers (nectarivorous). The effects of this trophic group can be negative (ants defend aphids against predators and aphids can be a problem for the plant by transmitting viruses) or positive (during nectar collection, ants can act as plant pollinators).

In order to detect differences in the structure of the communities in a multidimensional space we graphically represented the taxonomic (by species abundance, Fig. 14A) and functional (by trophic group abundance, Fig. 14B) community structure of each core site by performing a non-metric multidimensional scaling test (NMDS)

Fig. 14. Results of the NMDS analysis of (a) community taxonomic composition and (b) functional composition for ant plots. Each point represent a plot, the ovals depict the standard deviation of the point scores and the core site. Different core sites are represented with different colors: CS3 (INRAE, France), CS5 (INIA-CSIC, Spain), CS6 (WUR, The Netherlands), CS9 (CRAW, Belgium).

The different study core sites present significant differences in the taxonomic composition of the ant communities ($F= 53.193, p < 0.001$) (Fig. 14A) and in their functional traits related to ant diet ($F = 37.863, p < 0.001$) (Fig. 14B).

Fig. 15. Logarithmic abundances of ant trophic groups at different agroecological management practices in each core site.

Ant abundances did not show statistically significant differences between treatments,

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but due to the different taxonomic composition of ants in each core site, there are also some different trends in the abundance of the different trophic groups (Fig.15).

CS3 and CS5 are the only core sites with scavenger (insect-based diet) and granivorous (seed-based diet) ant species. At **CS3 (France)**, the most abundant species was *Tetramorium semilaeve* (48%), an omnivorous ant with a 75% insect-based diet and 25% seed-based diet. *Cataglyphis piliscapa* (22%) the second in abundance, is a thermophilous scavenger species with near 100% insect-based diet. The third more abundant species is *Pheidole pallidula* (16%), another omnivorous species with a similar diet than *T. semilave* (75% insect-based and 25% seed-based diet). And the fourth species is the Mediterranean granivorous *Messor barbarus* (12%), with its 100% seed-based diet. At **CS5 (Spain)**, the most abundant species is the granivorous *M. barbarus* (44%), followed by the two omnivorous species *Aphaenogaster senilis* (20%) (50% insect-based and 50% seed-based diet) and *Tetramorium caespitum* (11%) (75% insect-based and 25% seed-based diet). Other two relatively abundant species are the Mediterranean scavengers *Proformica nasuta* (9%) and *Cataglyphis iberica* (8%) (both with 100% insect-based diet).

However, in the northernmost areas, **CS6 (The Netherlands)** and **CS9 (Belgium)** the dominant ant species is *Lasius niger* (99.5% in CS6 and 100% in CS9), an aphid-tending ant (25% insect-based diet and 75% liquid food-based diet). At CS6 there is a second species in very low abundance, *Myrmica specioides* (0.5%), an omnivorous species with a 50% liquid food-based diet and 50% insect-based diet.

In Belgium and the Netherlands, *Lasius niger* is a pioneer species during forest succession (Boer 2004, Dekoninck et al2008), it is the only ant species that colonized and became established in the young forests resulting from natural succession on former grassland. On the other hand, in the Netherlands, Boomsma & van Loon (1982) observed a negative relationship between ant species diversity and the abundance of this pioneering ant *Lasius niger* in the dune grasslands. This negative relationship could probably explain the lack of an ant assemblage in the cereal crops at CS6 and CS9 sites. On the contrary, the absence in CS3 and CS5 of a dominant ant species

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provides to the ant species with a space that is, if not free, at least with a low level of competition, allowing the coexistence of different species forming ant assemblages, something that is usual in Mediterranean ant communities.

Finally, it seems that ant assemblages are relatively independent of local agroecological practices, because no significant differences have been detected between T1 (*first agroecological practice*), T2 (*second agroecological practice*) and T3 (*conventional practice*).

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Plate 1. The most abundant ant species in CS3 and CS5 sites. A. Queen and workers of *Tetramorium semilaeve*. B. Queen and workers of *Cataglyphis piliscapa*. C. Workers and a big-headed soldier of *Pheidole pallidula*. D. *Messor barbarus* carrying a panicle. E. *Aphaenogaster senilis* workers cooperatively carrying a dead bee. F. *Tetramorium caespitum*. G. *Proformica nasuta*. H. *Cataglyphis iberica*. Credits: A and G, F. Rodríguez (Faluke); B, N.J. Veerecken; C and D, X. Cerdá; E and H, F. Amor; F, Alex Wild. Blue bar is ~3 mm length.

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Plate 2. The ant species present in CS6 and CS9 sites. A. *Lasius niger* (credit: hormigueando.com). B. *Myrmica specioides* (credit: Quentin Willot). Blue bar is ~1.5 mm length.

Task 3.4. Identification of key attributes of soil food web structure which drive C cycling. Not yet started.

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